

**PROCESSES OF ORGANIZING THE METHODOLOGY OF PREPARING
FOR PIRLS ASSIGNMENTS THROUGH LIBRARY THERAPY**

Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi

Student of Termiz State Pedagogical Institute

+998770839702

Hasanovasabohat915@gmail.com

Abstract: While reading this article, you will learn about the methodology of preparation for PIRLS tasks through bibliotherapy and the direct support of bibliotherapy in self-healing and the use of bibliotherapy in overcoming social and emotional difficulties that may arise in elementary school students. considered.

Key words: PIRLS International Assessment Program, methodology, research, primary school students and teachers, therapeutic stories, bibliotherapy, understanding processes, Education, stories, fiction and non-fiction literature, human psyche.

We know that recently psychology and psychotherapy have developed a lot, and its new direction "Bibliotherapy", that is, the technique of treating the human psyche with books, has been applied to science. Everyone's mentality is different and some people want to develop themselves. For those who want to feed their soul, rediscover themselves and return to their originality, many therapy books can beautifully guide the way.

Today, together with the improvement of education, the process of education is becoming one of the topical topics. In this regard, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has always been thinking about another important issue - it is related to the manners, behavior and, in a word, worldview of our youth. Today, times are changing rapidly. Young people are the ones who feel these changes the most. Let the youth be in harmony with the demands of their time. But at the same time, he should not forget his identity. Let the call of who we are and the descendants of great people always resonate in their hearts and encourage them to stay true to themselves. At what expense do we achieve this? They say that education, education and only education. Therefore, we pedagogues are required to master the methodology of organizing education with education.

Bibliotherapy means treatment by reading books, that is, it is a type of therapy (treatment). In fact, this term has been used since ancient times. Books have been a form of therapy for people for many years, and recently the word "bibliotherapy"

has become popular. But due to the lack of local research on this topic, many people did not understand exactly what the topic means.

According to the emotional state when reading a book, a person learns to approach problems creatively. It shows people that there are other ways out. In the book, the person begins to compare himself with the characters given in the work. For example, distinguishing similarities and differences, directions of approach to events, and accordingly, he begins to use some characteristics and skills of the hero in his own way. This means the beginning of the path of self-development. One of the most important advantages of bibliotherapy is that a person who reads a book begins to fully accept himself. As time increases, self-confidence increases. That is why the use of bibliotherapy in primary classes is an effective way to form reading culture in students.

They feel how great the level of the book and knowledge is, and summarize their thoughts. In this process, the class leader can organize educational activities. As a result of the reforms implemented in our developing education system, huge economic growth indicators are being achieved, increasing the demand for skilled personnel and mature specialists in all fields. This in itself requires increasing the interest of our students in lessons and increasing the attention of teachers to all-round education. Developed countries consider the role of youth education in the development of society and human development to be important. That is why they pay special attention to the quality of education. At the same time, the concept of quality in the field of education became quite popular in our country. Increasing the intellectual potential of the future young generation and forming a broad worldview is important not only for a particular country, but also for the international community.

In general, bibliotherapy is used in combination with writing in adults and play therapy in children, which is characterized by making rehabilitation less stressful. Bibliotherapy is completed in 3 stages.

1. Adaptation and reflection. At this stage, a person gets acquainted with the events in the book, meets the characters, and compares the events with himself.

2. Emotional explosion - confrontation. After a certain time, a person begins to remember what he experienced. Sometimes it takes a certain amount of time, it seems to be relieved by remembering the past events.

3. Integration. This step is the last step. A person tries to look at events from a different perspective. Based on the events in the book, he wants to see himself in a more harmonious situation. He behaves more creatively in problem solving.

A book or educational material is medicine for the soul, and therefore it is a pharmacy that can be obtained based on the prescription advice of libraries and

librarians, psychologists, etc. It is necessary to be able to choose books that suit the family conditions, character and interests of students. a responsible and responsible person for the education of the generation. Libraries in Great Britain have bibliotherapists. They know the customer a little bit as an individual. They talk and ask what the client likes to read, allow them to learn how to better know and appreciate local libraries, and find books together that the client likes. This includes forming groups to discuss what has been read and having a cup of tea or coffee in front. On the table, libraries and librarians have long been engaged in activities related to bibliotherapy: helping people change their thoughts, feelings, or behaviors for therapeutic purposes, etc.

Research focuses on demonstrating understanding of how to apply knowledge to new projects and situations. The reader is an active participant in this process, creating meaning, reflecting on the text, and consciously choosing effective reading strategies. Each type of text follows typical patterns and rules to help the reader interpret the text. Any text can have different forms. These include traditional books, magazines, documents and newspapers, as well as written forms in digital form.

Bibliotherapy, a creative art therapy that involves reading stories or specific information, uses a person's content and relationship with books, poems, and other written words as therapy. In order to do this, we need to find out what the meaning of this work is through the conversation method, guide their thoughts and express their imaginations about how important it will be in their future lives. Increasing students' interest in bibliotherapy is not only the responsibility of the teacher, in this process, parents mothers should also take an active part. Reading books together improves the relationship between parents and children. When a person teaches his child to read books, he should first of all set an example in this work.

Psychotherapy supports bibliotherapy, which uses a standard manual to develop skills to regulate emotions through reading. In its most basic form, bibliotherapy is the use of books to help people solve the problems they face at a particular time. It consists in choosing reading materials that are suitable for the client's life situation. Bibliotherapy has also been explained as "a process of dynamic interaction between the individual reader and literature—an interaction that can be used for personal evaluation, adaptation, and growth." Bibliotherapy for adults is a form of self-healing in which structured materials are used as a tool to relieve grief.

At the Library of London, bibliotherapy is considered part of "Healing Medicine". The concept of treatment is based on the tendency of a person to assimilate with others through his expressions in literature and art. For example, when a child who reads a story about a child who loses a parent feels like something is missing in the world, or when a person in a bad mood reads a comic book, the

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

concept of bibliotherapy expands to self-help manuals without therapeutic interventions. or involves the therapist "prescribing" the film to the client as needed. In bibliotherapy, the works recommended to the reader with a certain character, his personal identification, appear without psychological risk, and this leads to a reasonable understanding of the relevance of the solution proposed in the text to the reader's own experience.

Each text and story selected for research should be a relevant topic for today. In the process of analysis, students should stop at both educational and educational conclusions. After all, our educational system is distinguished by the fact that education and upbringing are carried out organically. [3; 25-b] Participation in PIRLS allows Uzbekistan to independently objectively assess the level of reading skills among primary school students. In addition, the openness and integration of Uzbekistan's education ensures the integration of the world's leading educational systems into the international community.

Today, bibliotherapy is widely used in the American and European educational system. With this, they say that certain characteristics and skills are somehow formed in children. Through the stories given for reading by students, the client is helped to gain hope and release emotional tension, to correct their negative behavior by offering alternative, positive actions. increases wealth, improves brain activity, and causes new and unique ideas to come into the world.

Bibliotherapy relies heavily on self-help books, and there must be a connection between the situations in the story and the student's personal problems. Because this reading should make them think about themselves. Another benefit of bibliotherapy includes teaching youth to deal with problems, not being teased by students, teasing peers, fear, changes in sexual life. Bibliotherapy can consist only of reading or it can be supplemented with discussion and game activities.

Where necessary, bibliotherapy primarily used existing texts. Literature devoted to a specific topic related to the child provided source materials. There are 2 forms of bibliotherapy, they are clinical and developmental forms.

Developmental bibliotherapy is a useful tool to use before problems arise. This bibliotherapy is often used by teachers or parents. Many therapeutic stories are written for specific individual needs. But practitioners also use it to promote psychological resilience when groups and communities face challenges. For example, therapeutic stories can play a role in creating inclusive classrooms and work communities.

Books and reading are an integral part of young people's lives. Bibliotherapy does not assign meanings and is not a form of direct instruction. It is an invitation and permission to open wisdom and insight to more children. Otherwise, it can be

extinguished. Why should bibliotherapy be started from primary grades? Coming to school, we need to instill in the minds of young people, who are getting their first ideas about society, the knowledge that will be the basis for their spiritual growth and becoming a perfect generation... it is important to promote it in accordance with our mentality.

The use of bibliotherapy in the formulation of PIRLS studies can be the most appropriate choice.

In conclusion, it can be said that bibliotherapy helps a person to work with himself, to understand himself, to correct his mistakes by himself. Bibliotherapy is a supportive psychotherapy, in which the skills of emotional regulation by reading a selected standard manual are acquired through behavioral therapy or cognitive therapy methods. One of the trends entering Uzbekistan is bibliotherapy. I believe that it is necessary to promote it widely to the elementary classes, to the public, and to increase the number of additional literature. Because a book that many people consider lifeless can prove to them how illiterate they are.

References

1. Nevzat Tarxan. Masnaviy terapiya. Toshkent 2022. Yangi asr avlodi
2. Gualano, Bert, Martarona, Voglino. "Clinik Psychology International" 2017
3. Berns. Biblioterapiya 2004
4. Nishanova Z.T, Asomutdinova Sh. Psixologik maslahat. –T.: O‘zbekiston Faylasuflari ilmiy anjumani. 2010 -248 b.
5. Nishanova Z.T, Alibayeva Sh.T., Sherimbetova Z.SH. Psixologik xizmat Elektron darslik. –T.: 2012 y.
6. "THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PEARLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION" Interneshional Journal of Studies in Advanced Education Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi Volume 3, Issue 5, May – 2024
7. Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi "Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalarning o‘zlashtirishida biblioterapiyaning o‘rni" Ta’lim tizimida psixologik xizmatning zamonaviy tendensiyalari: Nazariya va amaliyoti Respublika II ilmiy – amaliy konferensiyasida 2023
8. Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi "Ona tili va o‘qish savodxonligi darslarida PIRLS xalqaro baholash dasturini takomillashtirish" Zamonaviy Boshlang‘ich ta’lim innovatsiyalar, muammolar va rivojlantirish istiqbollari xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyada 2023

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

9. Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi “O’qish savodxonligi darslarida pirls hikoyalarini qo’llash metodikasi” “integrational conference on interdiscinlinary science” 2024
10. Kichik yong‘oq daraxti |Mat|: / Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi "KITOB NASHR" - 2024-yil. 105 b.
11. PIRLS TADQIQOTLARIGA TAYYORLOV JARAYONIDA INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH for patriciation in the scientific-online conference "INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MEDICINE, SCIENCE AND EDUCATION" with an article entitled 26.03.2024 Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi
12. O’QUVCHILARNING IJOBIY FAZILATLARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA PIRLS XALQARO BAHOLASH DASTURINING AHAMIYATI, INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON MULTIDISCIPLINARY SCIEN 26.03.2024 Hasanova Sabohat Komil qizi
13. “MECHANISMS FOR USING THE NEW TEXTBOOKS IN THE PLANNING OF PEARLS ASSIGNMENTS” Hasanova daughter of Sabohat Kamil 24th - International Conference on Research in Humanities, Applied Sciences and Education Hosted from Berlin, Germany <https://conferencea.org> April 27th 2024
14. “METHODOLOGY OF USING NEW TEXTBOOKS IN ORGANIZING PEARLS TASKS (AS AN EXAMPLE FROM NATURAL SCIENCE)” Hasanova Sabohat International Conference on Advance Research in Humanities, Sciences and Education <https://confrencea.org> Hosted from London, The UK March 30th 2024